

Challenges in Detecting and Analyzing EEG Error-Related Potentials: Lessons from a Case Study in HRI

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Abstract—Recently, electroencephalographic (EEG) signals have been used to enhance Human-Robot Interaction (HRI). In particular, Error-Related Potentials (ErrPs) have been exploited since very few years. These potentials are evoked when there is a mismatch between the command given by the subject and the movements of the robot, or if the user’s expectation is different from the robot or other human behavior. These signals can be used to improve and customize the robot system, as feedback to better adapt the robot to human needs. This work aims to investigate and detect the ErrPs during different interaction tasks. We set up an experiment divided into five different tasks, where every task has 120 events with a 25%-35% probability of error. The robot used in the experiment is a Baxter robot and the commands from the subject to the robot are sent in two different ways: with a keyboard or with a motion capture device. This work aims to reproduce a simplified teleoperated pick and place task. However, the achieved results do not allow to correctly identify the ErrPs, but exhibit only some minor differences between trials with and without errors. Hence, we here analyze the reasons behind such negative results, focusing on the challenges of the structure and the setup of the experiment. We analyze the possible problems and provide some recommendations to overcome them in similar use cases.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in utilizing EEG signals for Human-Robot Interaction (HRI). A specific type of EEG signals are the so-called Event-Related Potentials (ERP), and the Error-Related Potentials (ErrP). An ERP is the brain response aroused as a result of a specific event, while ErrPs are evoked involuntarily when the subject perceives an error during the use of a system, while interacting either with a robot [1] or with another human [2]. The literature on the use of ErrPs in HRI usually involves scenarios where a subject issues a command to a robot, and the robot executes a corresponding movement. If the movement corresponds to the command given by the subject, no ErrPs can be observed from the EEG measurements; instead, if the movement of the robot is different from the command, an ErrP can be seen in the EEG data [3].

As a result, ErrPs can be used as implicit human feedback signal to the robot to assess erroneous or unexpected actions from the human perspective [4], [5]. In these applications,

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a crucial aspect is the reliability of the interaction system, since it requires both the adaptation of the robot’s behavior to the human, and the human adaptation to the robot [6]. Several studies have explored the application of ErrPs in different domains in order to facilitate robot adaptation in HRI. The detection of ErrPs has been used in the control of a humanoid robot or drone [7], or to control the movement of a neuroprosthetic device [8] by adapting its velocity and position based on the human brain response and letting the robot learn a human-desired end-effector trajectory. These signals have also been used in Inverse Reinforcement Learning (IRL), in order to maximize reward functions to recognize and replicate human gestures [9]. In this context, if the robot executes a movement specified by the user, it receives positive reinforcement; however, an erroneous movement triggers the ErrP and results in negative feedback, enhancing the overall performance of the robotic system. Furthermore, ErrPs have found application in pick-and-place tasks for individuals with tetraplegia [4] and to infer subject preferences on robot trajectories [10]. An example involving robot learning of control policies for singularity avoidance based on ErrPs has been recently proposed [11], while the feasibility of using EEG-based neuro-cognitive measures for online robot learning of dynamic subtask assignment and planning robot trajectories has been explored in [12]. Within the realm of Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs), continuous EEG recording has been employed to facilitate real-time control over the movements of a robot [9].

In order to achieve these goals, a necessary requirement is the correct detection of the ErrP [13]. The classification of ErrPs can be performed either online or offline, involving post-processing or in-the-loop methods. The best classification method is offline with post-processing, because it allows for the utilization of more extensive data and computation time. However, the goal of many studies is to achieve effective classification in a closed-loop online setting, aiming to directly harness the brain’s response. Indeed, a significant advantage of ErrPs lies in their involuntary nature, obviating the need for conscious effort. Implementing a closed-loop online approach enables real-time decoding without interrupting the robot’s movements, leading to enhancements and customization of the robotic system [3].

The detection of ErrPs is possible due to their distinctive waveform, characterized by specific peaks and associated latencies. The latency is determined from a reference time instant, established when the robot initiates its movement. The ErrP waveform is characterized by an initial positive

peak occurring between 50-100 milliseconds after the robot starts moving. Subsequently, there is a negative peak within the 200-500 millisecond range, followed by another positive peak occurring between 300-500 milliseconds [1], [14]. These peaks are denoted by “P” or “N” representing positive and negative amplitude, respectively. Following the letter designation, a number is assigned to indicate the latency, resulting in peak sequences such as P100, N200, and P300.

In the literature, no guidelines can be found for detecting ErrPs. Indeed, there are some studies on ERPs that highlight important steps for their detection. For example, the study by [15] focuses on measuring latency, while in [16] different protocols are considered to correct ERP latency. Moreover, there is a study with guidelines to elicit and record ERPs in clinical research [17]. However, these studies focus on ERPs only. Conversely, our work aims to provide guidance for ErrP detection.

II. AIM OF THIS WORK

The aim of our work is to identify and analyze ErrPs within the context of HRI. In particular, we underscore the potential challenges arising from an inappropriate experimental protocol or inaccurate processing and recording methods, during the detection of ErrPs.

To this end, we consider different types of teleoperation tasks, where the robot is expected to reproduce the commands provided by the human. Mismatch between robot’s movements and human actions are intentionally introduced to elicit ErrPs. However, upon scrutinizing the results during an offline classification processing, we were not able to observe the typical waveform of ErrPs in response to robot erroneous movements. Hence, in this paper we investigate the issues and criticalities related to experiments involving ErrPs in HRI settings. To thoroughly understand the challenges involved, we conduct a comprehensive analysis, scrutinizing both the technologies utilized and the experimental framework employed.

The setup of experiments is presented in Section III-A, the experimental protocol is shown in Section III-B and the processing of signals is reported in Section III-C. The results are, then, presented in Section IV. Finally, in Section V-A we describe the limitations of this study and highlight the precautions that must be considered during the detection of ErrP.

Ultimately, the objective of this work is to offer practical suggestions and comprehensive guidelines. By doing so, we aim to streamline and improve the successful implementation of future studies in HRI that incorporate ErrP detection, thereby progressing the comprehension and integration of this methodology in HRI.

III. METHODS

A. Setup

We designed an experiment aimed at evoking and analyzing ErrPs within the context of HRI scenarios. Seven participants were enrolled, consisting of five males and two females. Among the participants, two were at their first

Fig. 1. Experimental setup used during the interaction tasks.

experience collaborating and interacting with a robot, and the other five had familiarity with the use of robots. The participants’ ages exhibit a mean and standard deviation of 28.143 and 3.848 years, respectively. Before the beginning of the experiment, written informed consent was obtained in accordance with the principles outlined in the Helsinki Declaration, ensuring ethical compliance. All collected data were anonymized to protect the privacy of the participants. It is noteworthy that, while the number of subjects considered in this study is quite small, it is in line with the literature, since the number of subjects enrolled in existing studies relying on ErrPs varies from 7 to 12. For example, in [18] eight subjects have been considered only.

EEG signals were recorded using a neural helmet, specifically the “Enobio 20”, equipped with 19 electrodes: Fp1, Fp2, P7, P4, Cz, Pz, P3, P8, F3, Oz, T8, F8, C4, F4, Fz, C3, Fpz, T7, F7. In particular, the setup included 17 dry electrodes and 2 gel electrodes. The electrodes were located according to the international system 10/20 [19]. There are other works with a small number of electrodes [20], [21]. The electrode Fpz was a reference electrode and the left ear lobe was used for the ground. Data were recorded using Neuroelectronics software NIC2¹ on a PC (Intel Core i5 CPU@2.50GHz, running Windows 11 64-bit), with a sampling rate of 500 Hz. A dedicated PC was used to control the robot.

The experiment consisted of different tasks where the participants collaborated with a robot. To this end, we used a collaborative robot, namely the Baxter from Rethink Robotics. This is a collaborative humanoid robot, with a display as a face and two arms. The subjects interacted with the robot in different ways: with a PC keyboard or a motion capture system to create a teleoperation system based on gesture detection. The motion capture system we used is the Vicon, with markers placed on the chest and the right wrist of the subject. The experimental setup is reported in Fig. 1.

B. Experimental protocol

The experiment was divided into five different tasks, each involving collaboration between the participant and the robot.

¹<https://www.neuroelectronics.com/solution/software-integrations/nic2>

These tasks aim to replicate challenges related to pick-and-place actions and teleoperation. The complexity of the tasks incrementally increases, with participants completing them in a consistent order. The overarching goal was to command and oversee the robot’s movements, verifying their correctness through visual observation. An incorrect robot movement is defined as an action not chosen by the participant for each task, and is expected to determine an ErrP in the recorded EEG data.

The tasks are described as follows:

- Task 1: Commands are input through the keyboard by pressing “r” or “l”, and are expected to correspond to right or left rotations of the right arm of the robot, respectively.
- Task 2: Keyboard commands involve pressing “o” or “c”, and are associated to the opening or closing of the gripper of the robot, respectively.
- Task 3: Commands are given with the motion capture device, which detects the movement of the right wrist of the participant. The subject moves their wrist with right or left rotations, and it is expected that the robot replicates the movement accordingly. This task mirrors the first task but utilizes a motion capture device for command input instead of a keyboard.
- Task 4: Commands are given through the keyboard by pressing “r”, “l”, “u”, “d”, “o”, “c”, and are associated to robot’s movement towards right, left, up, down and gripper opening and closure, respectively. This task simulates a pick-and-place scenario.
- Task 5: Commands are issued via the motion capture device, involving right and left rotations. Participant movements are associated to up and down movements of the right arm of the robot. This task further explores teleoperation using the motion capture device.

For each task, we considered 120 trials, for each participant. In order to reproduce an error, we set a random probability of error between 25% - 35%, as used in the literature [3], [5]. Consequently, the number of “error” epochs ranged between 30 and 40 for each set of 120 epochs. Their presentation order was also selected randomly. The detailed experimental design is reported in Fig. 2.

The total duration of the experiment was about three hours. The first hour was for preparing the helmet, cleaning the electrodes, having the subject wear the helmet, and explaining the experiment. After that, before every task, an explanation was given about what the subject was expected to do during the task. Furthermore, before each task involving the motion capture device, a calibration procedure was required. After setup, the first task had a duration of 18 minutes, the second task had a duration of 7 minutes, the third task 20 minutes, the fourth task 12 minutes, and the fifth task 15 minutes. Moreover, the tasks involving the motion capture device often required multiple repetitions, due to loss of device calibration or correct communication with the robot.

Fig. 2. Experimental design used during the interaction tasks.

C. Processing

EEG recordings were processed with Matlab2023a and EEGLAB2023.0 toolbox. Figure 3 shows the processing pipeline.

As mentioned in Section III-A, our experiment utilized two separate PCs, one for robot control and the other for EEG recording. As a result, it was required to synchronize the EEG recordings with the robot’s movements. EEG recordings were divided into epochs, which are time windows with duration between 0.8-1.2 seconds [9] starting a few milliseconds before the start of the robot’s movement. Since ErrP

Fig. 3. Pipeline for EEG signals processing to detect ErrPs in the considered HRI experimental tasks.

components are time-locked, any difference, although small, between the beginning of an epoch and the actual robot’s movement causes a misinterpretation of brain activity and, hence, reduces accuracy in the detection of ErrPs. To this end, to guarantee precise synchronization between robot’s movement and EEG recording, we used an accuracy of microseconds (μs).

Following epoch synchronization, EEG signals were downsampled from 500 Hz to 256 Hz. Then, bad channels were removed by kurtosis calculation and data were filtered with the common average reference (CAR) filter. As a next step, following the literature [9], [22], we used a FIR band-pass filter with a Hamming window and cutoff frequencies of 0.5 Hz and 10 Hz to remove low-frequency drift, power noise, and high-frequency muscle activity. We then used the EEGLAB toolbox to eliminate artifacts through independent component analysis (ICA) and segment signals in single epochs. In particular, we categorized the epochs into “correct” and “error” based on robot movements, as detailed in Section III-B. The “error” epochs are expected to contain ErrPs, since they represent EEG signals recorded when a mismatch between the participant’s action and the robot’s movement was intentionally introduced by the experimental protocol. In contrast, “correct” epochs represent instances when the robot’s movement corresponded to the participant’s command. We then did a baseline correction [1], [21] and, finally, we averaged all the epochs of the two groups, “correct” and “error”, for all subjects, for each channel, to increase the signal-to-noise ratio [2], [8], [14]. As a result, it was expected that the average “error” epoch exhibit the typical ErrP waveform.

Fig. 4. Grand average epochs of all the study participants for the channel Cz for each task. The black line depicts the average “correct” epoch, while the red line depicts the average “error” epoch.

IV. RESULTS

Following the literature, the expected results are a specific waveform for signals classified as “error”, as reported in Section I. In particular, this waveform is composed of different peaks with a specific latency: P100, N200, P300. Due to the limited number of available signals for each subject, we computed the grand average over all the subjects together. We qualitatively evaluated the averaged signals, focusing on the Cz channel because it is the most common channel used in the literature [12], [21], [23]. However, it was not possible to detect such a waveform in the averaged “error” epoch. In Fig. 4, we show the grand average of “error” and “correct” epochs in red and black, respectively, for channel Cz and for each task. Epochs were averaged over 570 “correct” epochs and 240 “error” epochs, recorded during the different tasks for all the subjects together. A difference can be observed between the two signals, with the “error” signal exhibiting a greater amplitude than the “correct” one, as expected according to the literature [2], [22]. However, the epochs with error do not exhibit the typical waveform of ErrPs reported in the literature. It is possible to see in Task 3 a negative peak around 0.7 seconds and a positive peak around 0.8 seconds, but this does not represent a complete ErrP waveform.

Additionally, we performed a statistical analysis in order to confirm that there are no significant differences between the two conditions. Performing a t-test on the grand average

of “error” and “correct” every task, we did not obtain any relevant significance. We report below the results of the statistical analysis for each task, considering channel Cz for all subjects:

- Task 1: p-value 0.468
- Task 2: p-value 0.426
- Task 3: p-value 0.421
- Task 4: p-value 0.431
- Task 5: p-value 0.312

V. DISCUSSION

Analyzing the reasons behind the achieved results, we found different problems related to both the structure of the experiment and the used technologies. We deepen the analysis of criticalities and limitations in the next section, in order to provide practical suggestions and comprehensive guidance.

A. Limitations of the study

Firstly, it should be pointed out that the study enrolled 7 participants only. However, similar studies in the literature consider a similar number of enrolled subjects, usually including from 7 to 12 subjects. For example, the study in [18] includes only 8 subjects. Moreover, the participants in our study had different age and gender. Consequently, the collected dataset was not homogeneous. It is known from the literature that consistent differences in brain activity are reported as age and gender vary [20], [24]. A further limitation of the present study lies in the number of electrodes, since we used 19 electrodes. While there are other studies in the literature with a small number of electrodes (for example in [20] 11 electrodes were used, while in [24] 14 electrodes were used), most studies used from 32 to 64 electrodes [9]. A greater number of electrodes improves the quality of recorded signals, also because it becomes possible to add the channel FCz, which is not possible to use with a 10/20 system configuration and a small number of electrodes. Consequently, the detection of ErrP can be more accurate. Moreover, using more channels it is possible to improve the preprocessing of signals; for example, electrooculographic channels placed near the eyes can be used to remove eye movement-related artifacts. The availability of a greater number of channels increases the spatial resolution of recorded brain activity and improves the effectiveness of averaging techniques, thus leading to increased signal-to-noise ratio of the preprocessed signal. Moreover, as mentioned in Section III-A, we used two different PCs, one to control the robot and the other to manage the EEG recording. As a consequence, we had to face the issue of synchronizing the robot’s movements and the recorded brain activity. However, *ex post* data synchronization might lead to inaccuracies of the process, with disruptive consequences on ErrP detection and analysis. Indeed, the ErrP signals are time-locked and the detection of ErrP waveform is strictly dependent on the onset of the event (i.e., robot’s movement); any inaccuracy in establishing the time relationship between EEG and the robot’s movements severely undermines the

quality of ErrP analysis. Specifically, since ErrP duration is about 600-800 milliseconds, a precision at least at the millisecond level becomes imperative. For this reason, we used an accuracy of microseconds for the synchronization of robot movement and recording. However, the poor quality of the achieved results suggests that such synchronization accuracy might be not enough.

Regarding the experimental protocol, we realized that our experiment was too long, in terms of overall duration. Indeed, each participant took three hours to complete the experiment. As a result, we observed that almost all the participants had a significant loss in terms of attention and engagement during the different tasks. Moreover, some of the tasks were perceived as boring, since the robot moved at low speed and the participant had to wait for the robot to complete its movement and return to the home position, before a new trial was started. Although there are other experiments in the literature using the same robot, their structure is different and shorter than ours (e.g., [4]).

The number of trials is another problem linked with the duration of the experiment. In fact, despite the long duration, the number of trials for every task is 120, and the probability of error was varied between 25% and 35%, which corresponds to 30-40 trials for “error” epochs, per participant. The number of trials for epochs with error was not sufficient to let the ErrP waveform emerge in a distinctive manner from background noise and brain activity. Indeed, in the literature, the number of epochs with error is usually in the range from 100 to 120. Conversely, our experiment was limited to such a smaller number of epochs to keep the overall duration within a reasonable time.

Regarding the structure of the experiments, again to limit the duration, we did not introduce an inter-stimulus interval. The inter-stimulus interval is a pause between two consecutive stimuli, and is usually introduced to separate the epochs. It allows to avoid overlapping epochs or having two different stimuli in the same epoch. In our experiment, we set the duration of epochs to 1 second. The lack of an inter-stimulus interval caused problems when the participant did not wait for the robot to return to the home position before providing the input command for a new movement. This resulted in a mismatch between participant’s input and robot’s movement, because the robot started the movement after it had completed the previous one.

Finally, limitations were also found regarding the technologies we used during the tasks. The motion capture system is a very sensitive technology and requires a dedicated environment for accurate tracking of the devices under analysis. Conversely, if the room where the experiment is carried out is occupied with other objects or robots, as a common laboratory setting, the motion capture system might detect them, failing to detect the movement of the wrist of the subject or requiring further calibration. Moreover, as mentioned above, the selected robot was slow in its movements, compared to the human speed to provide input commands and the limited complexity of the interaction task. It is likely that the use of a different robot with larger speed

limits would have avoided some of the above mentioned limitations.

B. Concluding remarks

In this study, we focused on the challenge of detecting and analyzing ErrPs within the context of HRI. Over recent years, ErrPs have gained prominence in HRI scenarios and BCIs. Their utilization aims to augment interaction dynamics and equip technological systems with the capability to comprehend and respond to human expectations. To this end, we designed an experimental study aimed to elicit such brain responses with different tasks, inspired to a teleoperated pick and place activity. However, although we could find some differences between the “error” and “correct” epochs, we were not able to observe the typical waveform of ErrPs.

From the study of the achieved results, we observed certain challenges and critical aspects. The insights gained from these observations and the lessons learned could prove valuable to the broader research community in this field. By sharing our experiences, we aim to contribute to the enhancement of the design and implementation of similar experimental studies, ultimately fostering advancements in the detection and application of ErrPs in the domain of HRI.

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